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МАДАНИЯТ ВА САЊАТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО | JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

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MUSIC CULTURE DURING THE RENAISSANCE

ANNOTATION

In this article, there are specific periods of development in the history of Central Asia, and historically, these periods of development are considered to be a period of gradual renaissance, along with the ideas that culture and art of the time of our great grandfather Amir Temur are connected with the development of ancient music. the manifestations of the renaissance period are discussed.

Key words: culture, art, renaissance period, musician, composer, khafiz, Darvish Ali duster, kungura, musical heritage, great scholars, musicologist theoretician.

УЙҒОНИШ ДАВРИДА МУСИҚА МАДАНИЯТИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада Марказий Осиё тарихида ўзига хос ривожланиш даврлари мавжуд бўлиб, тарихан бу ривожланиш даврлари буюк бобокалонимиз Амир Темур даври маданияти ва санъати қадимий мусиқа тараққиёти билан боғлиқ деган ғоялар билан бир қаторда босқичма-босқич уйғониш даври ҳисобланади. уйғониш даврининг намоён бўлиши муҳокама қилинади.

Калит сўзлар: маданият, санъат, уйғониш даври, мусиқачи, бастакор, Ҳофиз, Дарвиш Али дустер, кунгура, мусикий мерос, буюк олимлар, мусиқашунос назарийчи.

МУЗЫКАЛЬНАЯ КУЛЬТУРА ЭПОХИ ВОЗРОЖДЕНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье рассматриваются определенные периоды развития в истории Центральной Азии, и исторически эти периоды развития рассматриваются как период постепенного возрождения, наряду с идеями о том, что культура и искусство времен нашего прадеда Амира Темура связаны с развитием древней музыки. обсуждаются проявления эпохи возрождения.

Ключевые слова: культура, искусство, эпоха возрождения, музыкант, композитор, хафиз, Дарвиш Али дастер, кунгура, музыкальное наследие, великие ученые, музыковед-теоретик.

During the years of independence, the restoration of our spiritual values, the creation of our musical culture to a new level, created great opportunities for in-depth study and promotion of the work and activities of our great teachers, their unique performance skills. Every artist who has left an indelible mark in the history of the artistic and aesthetic culture of our nation, including the musical culture, without a doubt, fully embodies the spirit of the era in which he lived, the aesthetic taste, spiritual needs and skills of his fans, and with his works He tried to satisfy his spiritual needs.

There are specific periods of development in the history of Central Asia, in all spheres of science and culture, culture and art, urban planning, architecture, certain times have left their flourishing period and entered the world culture. , left a name in history with his great contribution to science. Historically, these periods of development were called the gradual renaissance period. The first renaissance period began centuries after the Arab conquest, from the VIII century to the XII century. The development of enlightenment in Turkestan since the middle of the 19th century has been recognized in history as the third renaissance period.

In this sub-topic, we will mainly focus on the development of the music of the Timurid era, Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi and the following periods, which are a special period in the development of Uzbek national music culture, and the place of the music of that time.

Our great grandfather Amir Temur, who is known from history, left a name for himself with his attention to culture and art, architecture and construction, beautification works and numerous efforts. The buildings he built, the gardens he created, art and patronage to the people of knowledge, the work of religious leaders in respect of honor has been honored. Among them, his contribution to musical art has a special place, and it is highlighted in many historians.

When we look at the details of history, we can witness the development of culture and art during the time of our great grandfather Amir Temur based on clear sources. The appointment of the great musicologist scientist Abdulkadir Maroghi as the leader of the court musicians brought from the Shosh state also proves that he is passionate about the art of music.

According to the 17th century music historian Darvish Ali, Khoja Abdulkadir Margani was from Isfakhan, and he was a great music master, composer and theoretician of the East of that time. When he came to Samarkand, he directed the palace theater and music. He created his own school in Samarkand, created many students and made a great contribution to musical development. There is information that he wrote the books "Zabrutul Advor", "Maqosidul Ilkhan" by his pen, and Davrish Ali also gives information about the creation of a music collection called "Miatayin".

Amir Temur is the owner of the third category of handicrafts in his tuzuk. He brings them to the state room and explains that the seats are fixed there. In the written sources, among the great composers and musicians of that time, famous artists such as Sayfiddin Nashi and Qutbi Noyi, Said Yusuf (Kubuz), Davrishbek are written. Amir Temur gave great importance to the participation of artists, and all kinds of art manifestations took part in these parties. These events. Clavijo, the Spanish ambassador, also explained in his book.

The culture and art of Movarunnahr rose to heights especially during the reign of Ulugbek (1394-1449).

Davrish Ahmadiy Qonuniy, Sultan Akhmad Nayi, who created in Samarkand during the time of Professor Abdurauf Fitrat Ulugbek, Hisari from Karakol, who wrote a musical treatise, Abu Vafo from Khorezm, musicologist and scholar Maulana Sahib Balkhi, composer Abdul Baraka from Shakhrisab, the famous musician Navoi's uncle Muhammadali G` like the Arabs, he took the famous artists of that time to his pen.

In the work "Tuhfatus Surur" written by the famous musician and musicologist Hafiz Darvesh Ali, Ulugbek Mirzoni is also considered a musical scholar. In the book "Mukhit ot-tavorik" he is mentioned as a composer of "Buldjiy", "Shodiyna" - (this has come down to us). It was shown that he created great musical works such as "Akhloqi", "Tabrizi", "Usuli Rovani", "Usuli Bahri". It is mentioned in the data that among the artists of the city there were also women with hair and dancers.

After the death of Ulugbek, the period of development in art moved to Khiv. Our great-grandfather Alisher Navoi was directly in charge of it, patronized by king and poet Husayn Baigaro. Navoi became the champion of art, literature and culture of all Movarounnahr, Khorasan and brought it to a new stage of development. During this period, the musical culture of the Uzbek people rises to a high peak. Great music teachers trained the most talented students. New tunes, songs, works related to the theory of music have appeared, talented musicians, composers, khafiz have matured. His teacher and friend, the great Abdurrahman Jami, wrote the work "Risola muziki" in this regard.

In this work, valuable information was given about the ancient status of the Uzbek people. Another contemporary scientist, Zainabiddin Al Husayni, wrote a music textbook entitled "Kanuni ilmi va omalga muzik" and dedicated it to Navoi. Nuriddin Margilani's treatise "Maqsadul Advor" (the goal of music science) also appeared. Navoi was not only a patron of artists, but also a musicologist and composer.

Zahiriddin Muhammed Babur tells in his work "Boburnoma" that he created a number of musical works, including "Naqshi" (songs) and "Peshrov" (music). Their nicknames also show that they are closely familiar with music, as they are connected to "Navo".

In the second section of the work "Mahbub-ul-Qulub" by Navoi, the mutrib and (singer) mughanni (composer) talks about the effectiveness and educational importance of the mutrib and mughanni's performances, and the flute, gijjak, tanbur, chang, also describes the qualities of musical instruments such as oud, rubob, qubuz, kanon, chaganda, etc.

In the work "Mezonul avzon", Navoi gives information about eight types of folk songs, such as tuyuq changi, Turkish dream song, mukhabatnama, mustahzad, and their weight characteristics. In the work "Khomsat-ul mutakhayirin" it is shown that Navoi paid great attention to the theory of music. In this work, Maulana Ali says that he is an incomparable musician and theoretician, and he commissioned him to write a theoretical textbook. In addition, it shows the works of musicologists such as Ustad Qulmuhammad, Khwaja Shahabeddin Abdullah Marvaridi, and Mawlana Binai. Navoi dedicated the work "Kholati Pakhlavon Muhammed" to the work of the great composer of his time, who made a great contribution to the improvement of the status of twelve.

Zahiriddin Makhhammad Babur also gave valuable information about the music culture of that time. According to him, masters Qulmuhammad, Abdullah Marvaridi, Husayn Udi, Darvishbek, Yusuf O`loni, Ghulam Modi, Sheikh Noyi, Sheikh Guli (Gijjak) became famous thanks to Navoi's help and care.

In his work "Badasoul", Zayniddin Vasifi wrote about the great development of folk art during the Navoi era, and mentioned musicians and composers such as Hasan Noyi, Ahmad G`ijjaki, Ali Kuchak Tanburi, Hasan Bolabani, Mirzo Bayram, Ghiyaziddin. names.

According to the information of Zainiddin Wasifi, when Herat was conquered by the Saravians, about five hundred artists moved to Movarounnahr, among them Qasim Ali, a female singer and musician (tugonia), Chagar Khanim, Said Ahmad, Gijjaki, Mukhibi. It is mentioned that there are Ali Bolobani, Hassan Udi, Husayn Nayi, Hafiz and singer and dancer Maqsud Ali.

Abdurauf Fitrat also played the musical instrument named "Shiray" created in Movaraunnahr and Herat in the 15th century by Maulana Yusuf Badi from Andijan, the musical teacher of Husayn Boyqaro and Abdul Qasim, adding a string of tanbur. Mahmud Shaybani, Abduqadir Margilani, Habibullai Changi, Muharrami Changi, Ali Shunqor, Mukhtar Shamsiddin drummer, Mehtar Imam singer, Alijon Gijjakily give information about the musical teachers of that time. At the end of the 14th century, in the 15th century, cultural life, including musical culture, developed in other regions and cities of Movarunnahr, such as Fergana, Tashkent, Bukhara, Kent, Khiva.

Umar-Sheikh Mirza, the ruler of Fergana (Babur's father), tried to gather artists in Andijan, his capital. Information about the "development" of the art of that time is given in Boburnama. Babur remembers Khoja Yusufiy and Vasidiy, composer and musician Shox Husain from Tashkent, among the teachers of the Andijan musical environment of that time.

If we look at the progress of the musical art of the 16th-17th centuries, we can see that after a number of changes in the middle, earlier shifts took place. Under the guidance of the great poet and musicologist of the 16th century, Najmiddin Kavkabi (died in 1576), the twelve statures were further perfected. According to Darvish Ali's story, Maulana Najmiddin Kavkabi, who studied in Herat, was brought to Bukhara by Ubaydullah Khan, where he created his own school and worked on performing Uzbek music. He made a great contribution to the science of music theory by creating the work of Kavkabi "Musical treatise", which trained such musicologists as Khwaja Muhammed Maulano Reza Samarkandi, Khwaja Hassan Nosari, Maulana Hassan Kavolabi, Baqi Jarrokh. At the end of the 16th century, in the 17th century, during the rule of the Shaibanis, Ubaydullah Khan brought artists from different places to Bukhara and left the court as an accomplished poet. In the school of Ahiy Garavi, the martyrs of Darvish Ali were educated in the school of Khoja Hamza Tashkondi, Khoja Baba Janchi, Darvish Mokhmudi Andijoni from different parts of Movarunnahr.

Darvish Ali, one of the great musicians, music historians and theorists of the 17th century, became a dustman. He created the work "Risolaiy muzyka" consisting of twelve sections. This work serves as an important source for studying the history of music at that time.

In it, statures, branches of statures, methods and music theory are discussed. The musical instruments of Darvish Ali's book in different eras are tanbur, chang, flute, koshnay, ganon, oud, borbod, rubob, qobuz, rud, gijjak, shirat, kungura, dutor, setor, trumpet, boloban, drum. provides extensive information about words such as , speaker, circle. During this period, works related to music theory, such as "Risola tun muziki", "Prisalam koramiya" were also written by unknown authors.

In the second half of the 17th century, the art of music came to be understood. The division of Movarounnahr into three khanates and emirates has a significant effect. As a result of this, divorces occur in the cultural and musical life. Despite this, the music and art environment of the Khiva khanate continued and achieved some successes.

If we sum up the musical culture of these renaissance periods, our musical heritage, which has been polished to its full extent in the last thousand years, is strong from history with its great scholars, composers, and theorists of musicology. gained fame and enriched the history of Uzbek music. Our sense of difference today is also a product of the work and creativity of our great grandfathers.

All types of our musical culture not only provide people with artistic aesthetic pleasure, but also provide knowledge about the secrets of the world, which are extremely difficult to express with scientific concepts, and closely help to perceive the reality of life through artistic aesthetic means.

Our great ancestors highly valued the importance of the art of music and singing in the development of the human personality and the education of noble human qualities.

In the years of independence, the revival of our spiritual values, bringing our musical culture to a new level, creates great opportunities for in-depth study and promotion of the creativity and activities of our great teachers of the past, their unique and unique performance skills. Studying the masterpieces of our musical culture and the lives and works of great artists who made a significant contribution to its development in creating the ideology of independence and promoting its spiritual culture among young people is deeply educational. and has educational value.

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ТОМ-II, НОМЕР-3

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